

INTER-REGIONAL PERFORMANCE ASSESSMENT OF ACCESS TO HEALTHCARE SERVICES ITALY AND DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION: WHERE NEXT?

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Key-words: Digital transformation; Digital divide; Healthcare regional inequalities; AI; Italy

JEL-codes: I10, I19

Introduction

The aim of the presentation is to examine the recent changes in the inter-regional performance assessment of healthcare services in Italy, with a focus on the role of digital transformation in healthcare. The Italian National Healthcare system is decentralized, with shared responsibilities between central and regional governments. The socio-economic, healthcare and health divide as well as a digital divide between the Northern and Central/Southern regions has persisted during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Methods

The paper examines with a narrative review approach the evidence on policies aiming to monitor socio-economic health inequalities at the regional level and discusses the role of digital transformation policies introduced in the SSN, particularly after the pandemic outbreak. The potential of AI-enabled healthcare apps in improving access to healthcare in Italy and related issues is also discussed.

Results

Both the central government and Italian regions use a combination of quantitative and qualitative indicators to assess healthcare performance and regional inequalities. The national recovery and resilience public investment plan adopted after the pandemic outbreak, provides a concrete chance to reduce these inequalities. Italy has improved its e-health systems

over time, investing, e.g., in monitoring health outcomes, fostering the use of telemedicine, particularly after the pandemic outbreak. AI-enabled healthcare apps have the potential to improve patient engagement and provide personalized health advice. However, further research is needed to evaluate their implementation, effectiveness, and impact on healthcare.

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.10053412